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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ МУЛЬТИМЕДИЙНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА

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USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Аннотация

Информационные технологии стали неотъемлемой частью нашей жизни. Сейчас практически невозможно найти сферу человеческой деятельности, где некоторые задачи не выполнялись бы с помощью компьютера и интернета. Активное использование информационных технологий наблюдается и в образовании.

Последние достижения в области высоких технологий предоставляют педагогам широкие возможности для совершенствования образовательного процесса и преобразования его в качественно новую основу. Стало возможным передавать информацию с помощью различных программных и аппаратных средств, позволяющих обрабатывать аудио- и видеoinформацию, то есть мультимедиа.

Abstract

Information technology has become an integral part of our lives. It's now virtually impossible to find a field of human activity where some tasks aren't accomplished using a computer and the internet. The active use of information technology is also observed in education.

Recent advances in high technology offer educator extensive opportunities to improve the educational process and transform it into a qualitatively new foundation. It has become possible to transmit information using various software and hardware tools that enable the processing of audio and visual information, i.e., multimedia.

Ключевые слова: мультимедиа, преподавание иностранных языков, аудио- и видеоматериалы, учебные мероприятия, электронные словари

Key words: multimedia, foreign language teaching, audio and video materials, learning activities, electronic dictionaries

Multimedia technologies play a significant role in modern foreign language teaching methods. The use of electronic dictionaries, encyclopedias, interactive textbooks and manuals, games, online resources, simulators, electronic presentations, etc., can improve the effectiveness of learning.

Traditionally, foreign language teaching involves imparting theoretical information and developing the skills and abilities necessary for successful communication within the subject. The use of multimedia can positively impact several aspects of the learning process. In classroom settings, teachers are not always able to devote adequate attention to each student, which can lead to a loss of motivation and a decline in knowledge, skills, and abilities. Multimedia can be used in the context of a wide variety of learning styles and is perceived by a wide variety of people: some prefer to learn through reading, others through listening, still others through watching videos, and so on.

The use of multimedia in foreign language classes enables a student-centered approach, promotes individualization and differentiation of learning, and thus stimulates student engagement, increases interest in the subject, and enables independent learning tailored to each student's age, psychological characteristics, and lan-

guage proficiency. "By working with multimedia, students can influence their own learning process, tailoring it to their individual abilities and preferences. They study the material that interests them and repeat it as often as necessary, which facilitates more accurate comprehension" [4].

One of the main advantages of using multimedia is that it enables students to organize diverse learning activities, providing various ways to expand their vocabulary and learn new utterances, improve the memorability of studied language structures and the relationships between these structures, and develop specific skills and abilities.

Using audio and video materials in class (songs, educational films on various topics, news programs, television programs, commercials, etc.) also contributes to the diversity of students' learning activities and allows for the artificial creation of a language environment, immersing students in the realities of another country, and thus developing not only linguistic but also sociocultural competence. Multimedia technologies allow students to not only observe prepared educational materials but also participate in their creation, transformation, and practical use.

Various online resources play a significant role in the modernization of education. Firstly, these resources

implement the principle of authenticity, an important element of modern foreign language teaching methods. The use of un-adapted texts from foreign newspapers and magazines, various websites, and other sources allows for the study of the language as it functions today. Chats, various types of internet telephony (Skype), instant messaging programs (ICQ, QiP), social diaries (LiveJoomal), social networks (Facebook), and video conferencing offer ample opportunities for effective language acquisition. These communication tools allow for live, immediate communication with native speakers. This also helps students immerse themselves in a natural language environment without additional material or time expenditures, and develop communicative competence.

It's important to note that online resources help make foreign language learning more engaging, as they allow teachers to vary the methods of presenting information and make learning more practical. Moreover, since online technologies are one of the most important sources of information in modern society, incorporating them into teaching helps students acquire the necessary skills to use online resources.

The integration of computer technology into the educational process helps improve not only students but also teachers, as it provides the opportunity to exchange methodological experiences with domestic and international colleagues.

One of the advantages of using multimedia is that they facilitate the optimization of the monitoring and self-assessment system, thereby facilitating the teacher's work and developing student independence. Computerized tests allow students to independently monitor their mastery of the material covered and, if necessary, review it.

Integrating multimedia into the educational process helps teachers and educational institutions save on resources. The advent of computerized classrooms, multimedia teaching aids, interactive whiteboards, and other multimedia tools reduces the need for printed materials and additional handouts.

It is important to note that the introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process can be both positive (promoting learning effectiveness) and negative (due to incorrect or inappropriate use of multimedia). Clearly, addressing the issues of appropriate and justified computerization of education must be comprehensive. Two possible approaches to integrating multimedia into the educational process are identified. The first is that "such tools are included in the educational process as 'supporting' tools within the framework of traditional educational methods" [2]. In this case, multimedia resources act as a means of intensifying the educational process, individualizing instruction, and partially automating teachers' work related to recording, measuring, and assessing student knowledge.

The introduction of multimedia resources within the second approach "leads to a change in the content of education, a revision of the methods and forms of organizing the educational process, and the construction of holistic courses based on the use of resource content in individual academic disciplines" [2]. In this case, knowledge, skills, and abilities are viewed not as

ends, but as means for developing the learner's personality. The use of multimedia technologies is justified when full learning is impossible or difficult without them.

When using multimedia in foreign language teaching methods, it seems appropriate to introduce them as "supporting" rather than primary tools, as the specific nature of foreign language teaching presupposes a key role for the teacher, who not only manages the learning process but is also a direct participant in it.

It is important to emphasize that excessive use of information technology can lead to certain negative consequences. For example, the widespread use of multimedia leads to a curtailment of social contacts, reducing social interaction and communication. Communication via various communicators (Skype, Facebook) is effective, but it cannot completely replace "live" communication.

The role of multimedia in interactive textbooks is ambiguous. Feedback in this case does not extend beyond the true-false parameter. Interaction, surprise, non-standard responses, and the collapse of meaning are completely eliminated, further emphasizing the need for teacher involvement in foreign language teaching.

Another drawback of overusing information technology is that when students are presented with different types of information simultaneously, they become distracted from some to follow others, missing important information. Complex presentation methods distract students from the material being studied, which again highlights the need to clearly understand and determine how deeply multimedia should be integrated into the learning process.

The use of multimedia technologies allows for the development and improvement of reading skills through direct use of online materials of varying complexity (both educational and authentic materials); the development and improvement of listening skills through authentic online audio texts; the refinement of monologue and dialogic expression skills through problem-based discussions of online materials presented by the teacher or a student, as well as the refinement of dialogic speech skills through the use of various oral communicators; the improvement of written communication skills by writing replies to correspondence partners; the enrichment of vocabulary with the vocabulary of a modern foreign language reflecting a specific stage in the development of a people's culture and the social and political structure of society, using authentic texts from the country of the target language; and the acquisition of cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette, the specifics of speech behavior of various peoples in communication, and the cultural characteristics and traditions of the target language country.

Working with a computer promotes increased interest in learning, makes it possible to adjust the presentation of learning tasks according to their level of difficulty, and rewards correct solutions. Furthermore, computers completely eliminate one of the most important causes of negative attitudes toward learning—failure due to a lack of understanding of the material—as students have the opportunity to use various reference

books and dictionaries. Working on a computer, students are able to complete a task with the necessary assistance.

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